

Effect of nitrogen level on grain yield of rice under bush fallow continuous rice cultivation in high rainfall

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Upland soils in Liberia are generally low in nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). We evaluated the yield response of some upland rice varieties to applied N under bush fallow continuous rice cropping systems in the high-rainfall forest zone.

Trials were conducted first in 1980 on Acrisol soils at Suakoko after thick bush was cleared during the 1979 dry season. Nitrogen levels were tested in main plot trials and replicated varietal tests were in subplots. Trials at the same site were conducted in the 1981 and 1982 wet seasons. In 1980 and 1981, N as urea was applied in two split doses. In 1982 it was applied in three splits. In each trial 18 kg P/ha was applied at seeding and 33 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied at time of N application in split doses.

In 1980, after the bush was cleared, all 5 varieties yielded more than 1.0 t/ha without fertilizer N. With application of 20 to 40 kg N/ha, 2 to 3 t grain yields/ha could be harvested. Some varieties lodged at 40 kg N/ha. Yield increased with level of N applied.

Grain yields in 1981, regardless of N levels or varieties, were lower than in 1980, but grain yields increased with N levels.

Similarly, third-year grain yields at all N levels and varieties were lower than in the first and second years (see table).

Local rice variety LAC23, which was grown in all 3 years, was used to estimate the yield response surface as follows:

$$1980: \hat{Y} = 1648.0 + 48.87x - 0.33x^2$$

$$1981: \hat{Y} = 798.7 + 17.01x - 0.10x^2$$

$$1982: \hat{Y} = 715.9 + 15.96x - 0.005x^2$$

(where $\hat{Y}$ = grain yield in kg/ha, and x = N level in kg/ha).

The equations indicated that the yield response to applied N in LAC23 was almost linear. However, the estimated yield increase (kg/kg N) decreased with

Yield response of rice varieties to nitrogen under bush fallow continuous rice cultivation in high rainfall area of Liberia.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha) in various nitrogen levels (kg/ha) and years						Mean
		0	20	30	40	60	90	
<i>1980</i>								
LAC23	95	1.6	2.5	—	3.1	—	—	2.4
4418	93	1.0	2.8	—	3.6	—	—	2.5
MRC172-9	86	1.1	3.1	—	3.3	—	—	2.5
IR2035-108-2	94	1.1	2.5	—	3.0	—	—	2.2
ROK3	88	1.5	1.8	—	2.4	—	—	1.9
Mean		1.3	2.5	—	3.1			
LSD (0.05) N × V			0.2					
<i>1981</i>								
LAC23	95	0.8	1.1	—	1.3	1.5	—	1.2
4418	93	1.0	1.3	—	1.4	1.7	—	1.3
C22	99	0.7	0.9	—	1.4	1.7	—	1.2
IRAT132	92	0.7	0.8	—	1.0	1.3	—	1.0
Mean		0.8	1.0	—	1.3	1.5		
LSD (0.05) N × V			0.14					
<i>1982</i>								
LAC23	104	0.7	—	1.2	—	1.7	2.1	1.4
SEL IRAT 194/1/2	86	0.7	—	1.0	—	1.5	1.9	1.3
LS(1)-19-1-1	107	0.5	—	0.9	—	1.5	1.9	1.2
TOX502-2SLR-LS2-5B	97	0.5	—	0.8	—	1.2	1.9	1.1
Mean		0.6	—	1.0	—	1.5	2.0	
LSD (0.05) N			0.12					
LSD (0.05) V			0.16					

increasing N levels as follows:

Year	N levels (kg/ha)	Yield increase (kg/kg N)
1980	20	42
	40	36
1981	20	15
	40	13
	60	11
1982	30	16
	60	16
	60	16

Yield data indicate that for the first rice crop after bush fallow 20–40 kg N/ha may be needed to harvest more than 2.0 t rice/ha. However, 1.0 t rice/ha could be harvested without added N. For the second and third rice crops, more than 40 kg N/ha may be needed to harvest 1.5 to 2.0 t rice/ha.

The economics of applied N in upland bush fallow continuous rice cropping systems have yet to be defined. N application alone will not maintain grain yields. Decreasing organic matter content, exchangeable cations, CEC, and soil pH may cause low yields in succeeding rice crops.

Nitrogen management for transplanted rice in rainfed lowlands

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A major cause of low transplanted lowland rice yields in India is low fertilizer inputs, especially nitrogen fertilizer. Uncontrolled water supplies in lowland areas cause erratic fertilizer response. We sought to develop appropriate technology for N fertilizer application for transplanted rice grown on rainfed lowlands.

The experiment was conducted at the Rice Research Station, Malan, during the 1980 wet season. Soil was loamy with pH of 5.85; medium levels of organic carbon, available N, and P; and high available N, and P; and high available K. Three-week-old Himdhan seedlings were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing. At puddling time, before transplanting, 40 kg each of P₂O₅ and K₂O/ha were applied.

Applying 60 kg N/ha significantly in-